

Conference Abstract

Cyanoprokaryotes biodiversity in nine shallow Bulgarian wetlands

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Received: 18 Sep 2019 | Published: 18 Sep 2019

Citation: Uzunov B, Stoyneva-Gärtner M, Gärtner G, Radkova M, Stefanova K (2019) Cyanoprokaryotes biodiversity in nine shallow Bulgarian wetlands. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 2: e46680. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.2.e46680>

Abstract

The results from the investigation of the phytoplankton in nine shallow wetlands, situated in Central and Eastern Bulgaria, conducted in the frame of recent projects related to identifying harmful algal blooms and algal toxins in the country are demonstrated. Therefore, the focus is on the cyanoprokaryotes and their toxigenic species in particular. The species were identified using conventional light microscopy, while for distinguishing the toxigenic species and strains PCR-based molecular methods were applied. Cyanoprokaryotes comprised about 30% of the total phytoplankton biodiversity of the studied wetlands and were unevenly spread among them. The presence and spread of toxigenic strains in the studied wetlands also did not show any strong geographical pattern. Taxonomic problems related with the evaluation of the real cyanoprokaryotic biodiversity and potential alien or invasive character of the morphospecies are discussed.

Keywords

cyanobacteria, cyanotoxins, phytoplankton

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Presented at

Vth International Congress on Biodiversity: „Taxonomy, Speciation and Euro-Mediterranean Biodiversity“

Acknowledgements

The study was supported by the Scientific Research Fund of the Bulgarian Ministry of Education through Project DH-13-9/17.12.2017 and Project KP-06-OPR06/2/18.12.2018, and COST ActionES 1105 “CYANOCOST- Cyanobacterial blooms and toxins in water resources: Occurrence, impacts and management”

Funding program

Bulgarian National Science Fund - Project DH-13-9/17.12.2017 and Project KP-06-OPR06/2/18.12.2018

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